

Job Attitudes as a Mediator of the Relationship between Leadership Styles and Organizational Success: An Empirical Investigation on Sadat University in Egypt

Author Details: Wageeh A. Nafei-
University of Sadat City, Menoufia, Egypt

Abstract

Purpose: The purpose of this investigation is to determine the mediating significant role of Job Attitudes (JA) in the relationship between Leadership Styles (LS) and Organizational Success (OS) at Sadat University in Egypt.

Research Design/Methodology: To assess JS, refer to (JS questionnaire, Judge et al., 2001; Best & Thurston, 2004, OC (OC questionnaire Allan & Meyer, 1990; Meyer, et. al., 1993), LS (LS questionnaire Bass & Avolio, 1990; Popper & Lipshitz, 2000; Jung & Avolio, 2000; Sarros & Santora, 2001; Avolio & Bass, 2002; Stone, et al., 2004; Vera & Crossan, 2004) and OS (OS questionnaire Simon et al., 2011). The data of the study was collected from the employees at Sadat University in Egypt. Out of the 692 questionnaires that were distributed to employees at Sadat University in Egypt, 420 usable questionnaires were returned, a response rate of 61%. Multiple Regression Analysis was used to confirm the research hypotheses.

Findings: The findings of the study indicated that there is a significant correlation between LS, JS, OC and OS. In addition to that, JS and OC have the advantage of increasing OS.

Practical implications: The main subject of the study were all categories of employees at Sadat University in Egypt. Self-reported measures were used to measure JS, OC, LS and OS. Considering the importance of employees' OC and their effects on effectiveness of Sadat University, policy makers should take necessary measures for the optimal provision of intrinsic and extrinsic job rewards to make their core workforce highly satisfied and committed.

Originality/value: The relevant literature shows that job attitudes, LS and OS are under-researched in the public sector in Egypt. So, the current investigation has contributed to improve the understanding of this significant issue. Besides, the study findings are discussed in perspective of practical implications. This research dealt with job attitudes in terms of its concept and dimensions, in addition to dealing with the role of LS in promoting OS at Sadat University in Egypt.

Keywords: job attitudes, leadership styles, organizational success

1. Introduction

As organizations continuously improve and evolve, the role of a leader becomes more demanding and important. Leaders are known to be visionary, influential, charismatic, and even altruistic. As a result, leaders play a significant role in building high-performing teams who have high levels of job satisfaction and organizational commitment. Leaders are facing greater challenges than ever before due to increased environmental complexity and the changing nature of organizations (Riaz & Haider, 2010).

In short, effective leadership is the main cause of competitive advantage for any kind of organization (Lado et al., 1992; Rowe, 2001; Zhu et al., 2005). Leaders are conferred the opportunity to lead, not because they are appointed by senior managers; they lead because they are perceived and accepted by followers as leaders (Boseman, 2008).

In fact, a leader is responsible for not only leading but also providing followers with the tools that are needed to accomplish organizational goals. In the event that a leader is unable to provide the adequate information or resources that are needed, a conflict may arise rooted in distrust and de-motivation. Thus, a leader's role is very delicate and every action or decision must be very strategic. Leaders can anticipate future likelihoods and plan alternative strategies to meet uncertainties. Such traits are common in historical leaders. This sense of anticipation is believed to be innate and cannot be learned (Riaz & Haider, 2010).

Job Satisfaction (JS) and Organizational Commitment (OC) are key job attitudes (George & Jones, 1997; Jehn et al., 1999; MacKenzie et al., 1998).

OC and JS differ mainly in the following (1) OC can be defined as the emotional responses that an employee has towards his organization; and (2) JS is the responses that an employee has towards any job. These two variables are highly interrelated as an employee may have positive feelings towards the organization, its values and objectives, but he may be unsatisfied with his job at the organization (Meyer et al., 2002).

OC and JS are interrelated; they have diverse attitudes. OC is the better means of constancy, belonging and permanence compared to JS (Lane et al., 2010).

2. Literature Review

2.1. Leadership Styles

Leadership is expressed or displayed through interaction among people. For one to influence, another must permit himself to be influenced (Jago, 1982).

Interestingly enough, most people don't seek to be leaders because “as you take the role of a caring leader; people soon begin relating to you differently” (Kouzes & Posner, 2003).

Leaders must embrace the importance of change and treating employees better in order for an organization to thrive in a global and competitive society. “In highly competitive, rapidly changing environments, caring and appreciative leaders are the ones to bet on for long-term success” (Kouzes & Posner, 2003).

Leadership programs have become the norm for many organizations who value strategic leaders. “By embracing our own opposites and getting comfortable with our contradictions, we build richer, deeper lives” and further states, “This is especially crucial for leaders, who must weigh multiple points of view, balance conflicting priorities, serve numerous constituencies, and make decisions about issues with no easy answers” (Schwartz, et al., 2010).

Many organizations build leadership programs around competency models, a list of core skills they expect all leaders to cultivate. Organizations need employees who can be molded into leaders who can influence others to complete tasks and follow the mission of the organization. Leaders are also able to empower followers by “making key behaviors automatic” (Schwartz, et al., 2010).

Leaders believe in change, energize organizations to innovate continuously, recognize the need for synergy, and emphasize the importance of unity and collaboration (Hallowell, 2011).

Transactional Leadership Styles (TALS) involve motivating followers through the exchange of rewards, praises, and promises. Transactional leadership is characterized by leader-follower exchanges, whereby leaders exchange things of value with followers to advance both the leaders' own and followers' agendas (Ivey & Kline, 2010).

Transformational Leadership Styles (TFLS) tend to influence workers more positively. While leaders initiate and drive organizational change, they manage the change only with the help of other change agents. These change agents operate with different change skills and competencies depending on particular requirements and circumstances (Rhodes, et al., 2008).

The effect of transformational leadership on subordinates centers on three leadership outcomes: (a) the ability of the leader to generate extra effort on the part of those being led, (b) subordinates' perception of leader effectiveness, and (c) their satisfaction with the leader (Pounder, 2008).

Within transactional leadership, three subscales are documented, contingent reward, management-by-exception – active, and management-by-exception-passive (Xirasagar, 2008).

In prior research, the proposed association of transformational and transactional leadership has been one of augmentation. The augmentation hypothesis argues that transformational leadership will significantly predict leadership criteria after controlling for transactional leadership. Bass and his associates' views on morality relative to transformational and transactional leadership do suggest that transactional leaders would be expected to engage in unethical practices more so than transformational leaders” and further state, “Judgments of a leader's ethical posture may play a particularly strong role in influencing follower satisfaction with the leader (Vecchio, et al., 2008).

Effective transformational leaders are able to motivate, empower, and build healthy relationships with their peers throughout an organization. “Over the last decade, considerable research effort has been invested into understanding the processes through which transformational leadership positively relates to follower attitudes, behavior, and performance” (Walumbwa et al., 2008).

When exploring the conditions under which transformational leadership weaves its effects on performance, research results show that “transformational leadership relates to follower identification with work unit and self-efficacy, which interacts with means efficacy to predict individual performance, thus representing a moderated mediation effect (Walumbwa et al., 2008).

Instructors displaying transformational leadership qualities in the classroom had a positive and significant influence on student perception of classroom dynamics measured in terms of the three leadership outcomes: extra effort, effectiveness, and satisfaction (Pounder, 2008).

The proposed association of transformational and transactional leadership has been one of augmentation. The augmentation hypothesis argues that transformational leadership will significantly predict leadership criteria after controlling for transactional leadership (Vecchio et al., 2008).

Employees with higher levels of power distance orientation are less likely to be influenced by transformational leadership behaviors alone and may instead need to be led via different or additional leadership styles. Individual-level cultural value orientations, and particularly power distance orientation, should not be ignored in studies of the impact of transformational leadership on followers across cultures” (Kirkman, et al., 2009).

Business leaders are under constant pressure to comply with their demands while maintaining the organization’s competitiveness in increasingly complex markets (Franken, et al., 2009).

2.2. Job Attitudes

2.2.1. Organizational Commitment

OC is a relative strength of a person’s identification and involvement with the organization, as reflected in (1) acceptance of the organization’s goals and values; (2) willingness to invest effort in the organization; and (3) a desire to belong to the organization (Porter et al. 1974; Mowday, et al., 1979).

OC is a multidimensional in nature, involving an employee’s loyalty to the organization, willingness to exert effort on behalf of the organization, degree of goal and value congruency with the organization, and desire to maintain membership (Bateman & Strasser, 1984).

OC is a feeling of dedication to one’s employing organization, willingness to work hard for that employer, and the intent to remain with that organization (Meyer & Allen, 1988).

A highly committed individual strongly believes in and accepts the organization's goals and values, willingly exerts considerable effort on behalf of the organization and strongly desires to remain a member of the organization (Dubin at al., 1975; Steer, 1977). High level of OC represents a positive manner that could add meaning to life for employees, increased performance, reduced turnover and absenteeism for organization (Mowday, 1998). High OC may blind some employees to the ethical problems in their organization (Hunt et al., 1989). Moreover, low levels of commitment are largely dysfunctional for both the individual and the organization. The costs of commitment outweigh the advantages at high levels of commitment. So commitment may be at moderate level where both individual and organizational needs may be balanced (Randall, 1987).

OC is a multidimensional concept that provides a comprehensive insight into the link between employees and work-related behavior. OC is an employee’s interest in, and affiliation to, an organization. Characteristics of OC include: (1) staunchly believing in and accepting the organization’s goals and values; (2) truly serving the organization, and (3) staunch affiliation to the organization (Meyer & Allen, 1991).

OC can be described as the factor that promotes the attachment of the individual to the organization. To put it differently, higher levels of performance and effectiveness at both the individual and the organizational level will be the outcome of the high levels of effort exerted by employees with high levels of OC (Raju & Srivastava, 1994).

OC means loyalty and intention to stay with the organization, besides personal interest towards the employment (Brewer, 1996).

OC refers to employees' feeling and levels of attachment to their organizations. If an employee desires to remain in an organization, exerts effort willingly, believes in and accepts to organization's values and goals, OC can be enhanced in an organization (Barlett, 2001).

OC is very beneficial for the organization as it reduces the absenteeism rate and turns over ratio, let alone enhancing the organization's productivity (Jernigan et al., 2002).

OC can be classified into three categories. They are affective, continuance and normative. Each category is related to the other and they represent employee's relationship with organizations. All of the types of commitment have implications for the decision to continue or discontinue membership of organization (Meyer et al, 2002).

OC is also interested in the employee's willingness to leave their organization (Greenberg & Baron, 2003).

OC reflects the work attitudes of employees toward the organizations in which they work (Silverthorne, 2004).

The employee who is highly committed to the organization contributes to the organization performance. Because it is linked with absenteeism, work effort and turnover OC is very important (Joiner & Bakalis, 2006).

OC is an individual's willingness to dedicate efforts and loyalty to an organization (Jalonen, et al., 2006; Wagner, 2007). OC is important because committed employees are likely to be more willing to make personal sacrifices for the sake of the organization (Vitell, & Singhapakdi, 2007).

OC widely is described as a key factor in the relationship between individuals and organizations (Sharma & Bajpai, 2010).

OC looks like a strong magnetic force attracting one metallic object to another and indicates the degree to which an employee identifies with the organization and wants to remain within the organization in the future (Awad & Alhashemi, 2012).

OC can be classified into three categories. They are affective, continuance and normative. All categories are related to each other and they represent employee's relationship with organizations and all of the types of commitment have implications for the decision to continue or discontinue membership of organization (Meyer et al, 2002). Employees can experience all three forms of commitment and the psychological states reflecting the three components of OC will develop as the function of quite different antecedents. They will also have different implications for work behavior (Meyer & Allen (1991).

In this study, we follow Meyer and Allen (1991) three dimensions of OC (affective, continuous, and normative):

- *Affective commitment* refers to an employee's continuing to work for an organization thanks to emotional attachment to, involvement in, and identification with that organization (Rashid et al., 2003),
- *Continuance commitment* refers to the commitment based on the costs that are associated with leaving a specific organization (Lee et al., 2001; Greenberg & Baron, 2003).
- *Normative commitment* relates to feelings of obligation to remain with the organization, i.e. employee with a strong sense of normative commitment remain in organizations because they feel they ought to do so (Ayeni & Phopoola, 2007, Omar, et al. 2008).

2.2.2. Job Satisfaction

JS is the pleasurable emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job as achieving or facilitating the achievement of one's job values (Locke, 1969).

JS has been one of the most widely studied concepts in management literature (Wilson, 1996).

JS is the feelings one has toward a job and its various aspects. It also refers to the difference between what one expects and what one actually experiences in return for the services offered (Rahim, 1982).

There are two major reasons for concern about JS (1) association of low levels of JS with low levels of satisfaction with life, poor mental well-being, and even poor physical health; (2) individuals get affected by JS in the workplace. This is because the negative effects of low levels of satisfaction may increase turnover, absenteeism, tardiness, decreased professional commitment, and lower quality of work (Noel, et al., 1982).

JS is the degree of favorableness with which employees view their work (Stewart, 1983). JS means how far people like (satisfaction) or dislike (dissatisfaction) their jobs (Spector, 1997). JS refers to the positive feelings that employees have towards their jobs (Schermerhorn, et al., 1997).

JS includes employee's overall affective state regarding estimation of all aspects of his or her job (Netemeyer et al., 1997).

The two-factor theory of JS influentially explains JS. It maintains that JS has two components; intrinsic job factors and extrinsic job factors. The former is characteristics of the worker personally including desire for achievement, recognition, responsibility, and advancement. The latter is characteristic of the organization and related to features of the job, such as supervision, salary, company policy and administration, and working conditions (Desselle, 1998).

JS refers to an employee's general attitude toward his or her job. An individual who is satisfied with his or her job holds positive attitude toward the job (Robbins, 2000).

JS is the pleasure gained from the assessment of one's job regarding the realization of job values. JS is a broad concept, it can be both intrinsic and extrinsic. If an organization gives opportunity for personal growth and accomplishment, it enhances an intrinsic motivation to employee; if an organization provides pay satisfaction or chances for promotion, employees have extrinsic motivation (Schwepker, 2001).

JS means how far the employee is satisfied with his present work taking into account satisfaction of many of his needs and wants (Finn, 2001).

Optimal performance needs employee's full potential at all levels in organizations; this emphasizes the importance of employee JS (Rothmann & Coetzer, 2002). JS is the degree of an individual's satisfaction with the internal or external aspects of his or her job (Bhuiyan & Menguc, 2002).

JS is detected and assessed in accordance to one's total feeling about their job and the attitudes towards various sides or facets of their job (Ivancevich & Matteson, 2002). JS stems from one's envision of their job under the influence of their own unique needs, values and expectations. These factors are highly esteemed by them (Sempane et al., 2002). JS is a positive (or negative) evaluative judgment one makes about one's job or job situation (Weis, 2002).

JS is the reaction to a job, regarding one's targets in a job in comparison with the actual outcomes that the job provides to the individual (Rothmann & Coetzer, 2002).

JS is a positive emotional reaction to a particular job (Oshagbemi, 2003). JS stresses one's feelings about his/her job or pleasure feeling about job (Crossman & Abou- Zaki, 2003).

JS is a sign of organizational effectiveness as most employers realize that the optimal functioning of their organization depends partially on their level of JS (Saari & Judge, 2004).

As JS is multidimensional, a worker may variably be satisfied with job, supervisor, pay, workplace, and so forth. A number of elements makes up JS, including salary, clarity of job responsibilities, relationship with colleagues inside and outside one's unit and organization, organizational climate, career development, opportunities for advancement, and general perceptions of work environment (Rosser, 2004). JS is not a unitary concept. An employee can be relatively satisfied with one aspect of job and dissatisfied with one or more other aspects (Kreitner & Kinicki, 2004).

JS means personal gratification from one's work, as well as pleasure and feeling of accomplishment employees derive from performing their jobs well (Elbert & Griffin, 2005).

JS is of interest for worker in organizations and those studying them. It is a salient variable in organizational behaviour research, as well as theory of organizational experience ranging from job design to supervision (Hong et al., 2005).

JS impacts both individuals and organizations. On the individual level, JS impacts stress (Zeytinoglu et al. 2007; Lambert, et al., 2007), and burnout (Oncel, et al., 2007). On the organizational level, however, JS impacts empowerment (Hechanova, et al., 2006), customer satisfaction (Homburg & Stock, 2004), service quality and performance (Park & Deitz, 2006), and OC (Al-Ajmi, 2006).

JS draws on the nature of the job, besides the expectation of an employee from the job (Hussami, 2008).

JS is explained as the feelings a worker has about his or her job experiences related to previous experiences, current expectations, or available alternatives (Zarea, et al., 2009).

JS is the amount of pleasure an employee has with the job (Dendaas, 2004), and can differ from employee to employee and is a subject widely researched in organizations (Farsi, et al., 2010).

JS is a multi-dimensional concept. Different researchers emphasize different facets of JS and measure them differently. Wood et al., (1986) emphasized four dimensions of JS (satisfaction with, information, variety, closure and pay). Churchill et al. (1974) developed seven dimensions of JS (satisfaction with: overall job, co-workers, supervision, company policy and support, pay, promotion, advancement and customers). Smith et al. (1969) focused a five dimension scale of JS (satisfaction with, type of work, the pay, opportunities for promotion, the supervision and the coworkers on the job). However, in the literature there is a different approach to measure satisfaction. Global scale of JS is composed of one single, integrated dimension. In this scale, respondents assert their overall feelings about the job (Spagnoli, 2012).

In this study, we follow Judge et al., 2001; Best & Thurston, 2004 with two dimensions of JS (internal satisfaction and external satisfaction):

- **Internal Satisfaction:** the opportunities to demonstrate abilities, sense of achievement obtained from work, ethical values of the work, opportunities to provide services.
- **External Satisfaction:** Job content, salary, unobstructed channels for promotion, work environment and equipment.

2.3. Organizational Success

"Success" in English, according to (Webster, 1974) means end your access to what is best, or access to excel.

In French, according to (Robert, 1983) "Reussite" means getting a new result, and the means to reach or attain higher. With respect to Organizational Success (OS), there is still some confusion and lack of clarity of methodological and procedural frameworks.

Regarding success through financial performance, operational productivity and efficiency, profits, target return, improvement programs in total quality management framework, re-engineering of reference and comparison is a narrow view that does not define success in the long-term in light of competitive markets. Success in the long-term lies in the organization's ability to do better things than competitors do. This is through owning distinct and fundamental capabilities that can not be imitated; besides ability to get on a competitive center of excellence (Hill & Jones, 2001).

Growth is an indicator for measuring OS. It means efficiency or the organization's ability to achieve its objectives in the long term, through expansion, renovation and survival (Whetten, 1987).

OS is the organization's ability to achieve long-term goals and balance between the goals and objectives of the organization of employees (Kenny, 2001).

OS is the organization's ability to coordinate activities in all components linking this to a common vision to achieve its strategic goals. (Dell & Kramer, 2003).

The basic elements of OS may be expressed in the form of an equation: OS = message + strategic goals + outstanding performance (Whitney, 2010).

There are two approaches for OS in all different organizations. The first approach to OS is the economic gateway. It is based on the competitive advantage stemming from the distinct market place. The first set for the performance of the organization is the external environment of the structure of the competition environment industry (Ambrosini, 2003). This includes approaches of forces of competition (Porter), innovation (Schumpeter), and scenario analysis which is characterized by a vision of the future opportunities and environmental threats, besides forecasting analysis of the competitive advantages (Grant, 2000).

The second approach to OS is based on the relatively modern resources approach, which confirms the possibility of looking at the organization as a package of resources to enable them to get a sustainable competitive advantage (Ambrosini, 2003). This approach is mainly based on a study (Selznick, 1957) about the distinctive competencies, and Penrose (1959) that the organization is a collection of resources and their performance depends on their ability to use these resources. This includes the approach of the value chain to analyze the strategic capabilities that can be converted into essential competencies that support competitive advantage analysis (Hitt, 2001).

3. Methodology

3.1. Research Model

The proposed comprehensive conceptual model is presented in Figure (1). The diagram below shows that there is one independent variable of OA. There is one dependent variable of JE. It shows the rational links among the variables. The research model is as shown in the following figure.

Figure (1)

Proposed Comprehensive Conceptual Model

The research framework suggests that JA (JS and OC) plays a significant role in the relationship between LS and OS.

JS is measured in terms of the internal satisfaction and external satisfaction (Judge et al., 2001; Best & Thurston, 2004).

OC is measured in terms of affective commitment, continuance commitment and normative commitment (Allan & Meyer, 1990; Meyer, et. al., 1993).

LS is measured in terms of contingent rewards, management by exception, individualized consideration, charismatic-inspiration, intellectual stimulation (Bass & Avolio, 1990; Popper & Lipshitz, 2000; Jung & Avolio, 2000; Sarros & Santora, 2001; Avolio & Bass, 2002; Stone, et al., 2004; Vera & Crossan, 2004).

OS is measured in terms of organizational survival and organizational growth (Simon et al., 2011).

3.2. Research Questions and Hypotheses

The researcher found the research problem through two sources. The first source is to be found in previous studies, and it turns out that there is a lack in the number of literature reviews that dealt with the analysis of the relationship among LS, JS, OC, and OS at Sadat University in Egypt. This called for the researcher to test this relationship in the Egyptian environment. The second source is the pilot study, which was conducted in an interview with (30) employees in order to identify the relationship among LS, JS, OC, and OS. The researcher found through the pilot study several indicators notably the important and vital role that could be played by LS in reinforcing OS at Sadat University in Egypt. As a result of the discussions given above, the research questions are as follows:

Q1: What is the nature and extent of the relationship between LS (contingent rewards, management by exception, individualized consideration, charismatic-inspiration, intellectual stimulation) and JA (JS and OC) at Sadat University in Egypt.

Q2: What is the nature of the relationship between JA (JS and OC) and OS at Sadat University in Egypt.

Q3: What is the extent of the relationship between LS (contingent rewards, management by exception, individualized consideration, charismatic-inspiration, intellectual stimulation) and OS at Sadat University in Egypt.

There are studies in literature that study LS, JA, and OS factors separately and within the frame of bilateral relation but there is no study that examines these three factors collectively at the Egyptian environment. This study aims to contribute to the literature by examining the research variables collectively and reveal the interaction among the research variables. As a result of the discussions given above, the following hypotheses were developed to test the mediating significant role of JA in the relationship between LS and OS at Sadat University in Egypt.

The following hypotheses were developed to test if there is significant correlation between LS, JA and OS.

H1: LS (contingent rewards, management by exception, individualized consideration, charismatic-inspiration, intellectual stimulation) has no statistically significant effect on JA (JS and OC) at Sadat University in Egypt.

H2: JA (JS and OC) has no statistically significant impact on OS at Sadat University in Egypt.

H3: LS (contingent rewards, management by exception, individualized consideration, charismatic-inspiration, intellectual stimulation) has no statistically significant influence on OS at Sadat University in Egypt.

3.3. Population and Sample

The study subjects are employees at University of Sadat City in Egypt. The total population is 692 employees. The research population is illustrated in the following table:

Table (1) Distribution of the Sample Size

Faculty Members	Number	Percentage
1. Faculty of Veterinary Medicine	137	19.8%
2. Faculty of Tourism & Hotels	89	12.9%
3. Genetic Engineering Research Institute	117	16.9%
4. Faculty of Physical Education	174	25.1%
5. Faculty of Education	33	4.8%
6. Faculty of Commerce	55	7.9%
7. Faculty of Law	43	6.2%
8. Institute for Environmental Studies and Research	44	6.4%
Total	692	100%

Source: Staff Members Affairs Department, Sadat University, Egypt, 2014

Due to the small number of members of the research community at the University of Sadat City, it was decided to study this community using comprehensive inventory (Complete Numeration or Census) in order to get the highest percentage of survey lists. Table (2) provides more detailed information about the sample and the measures.

Table (2) Characteristics of the Sample Units

Variables	Number	Percentage	
1- Sex	Male	220	52.4%
	Female	200	47.6%
	Total	420	100%
2- The Academic Degree	Professor degree	70	16.7%
	Associate professor	102	24.3%
	Assistant professor	133	31.7%
	Lecturer	45	10.7%
	Demonstrator	70	16.7%
	Total	420	100%
3- Marital Status	Married	313	74.5%
	Single	107	25.5%
	Total	420	100%
4- Age	Less than 30 years	61	14.5%
	From 30 to 45	192	45.7%
	More than 45	167	39.8%
	Total	420	100%
5- Period of Experience	Less than 5 years	203	48.3%
	From 5 to 10	138	32.9%
	More than 10	79	18.8%
	Total	420	100%

3.4. Procedure

The goal of this study was to identify the relationship between LS, JA and OS at Sadat University in Egypt. A survey research method was used to collect data. The questionnaire included four questions, relating to LS, JA, OS and biographical information of employees at the Egyptian industrial companies. Data collection took two months. Survey responses were 61%, 420 completed surveys out of the 692 distributed.

3.5. Research Variables and Methods of Measuring

3.5.1. Leadership Styles Scale

The present study has investigated LS as an independent variable. The researcher has drawn on the scale of Bass & Avolio (1990) for measuring LS. Twenty-five statements have been modified upon reading a host of studies including (Popper & Lipshitz, 2000; Jung & Avolio, 2000; Sarros & Santora, 2001; Avolio & Bass, 2002; Stone, et al., 2004; Vera & Crossan, 2004). There were 5 statements measuring contingent rewards, 5 statements handle management by exception, 5 statements illustrate individualized consideration, 5

statements handle charismatic-inspiration, 5 statements illustrate intellectual stimulation. The survey form has been used as a key tool to collect data to measure organizational success at Sadat University in Egypt.

3.5.2. Job Satisfaction Scale

The researcher will depend on the scale developed by (Judge et al., 2001; and Best & Thurston, 2004), in measuring JS, which has been divided into two main components (internal satisfaction and external satisfaction). There were five items measuring internal satisfaction and five items measuring external satisfaction. The survey form has been used as a key tool to collect data to measure organizational success at Sadat University in Egypt.

3.5.3. Organizational Commitment Scale

The researcher will depend on the scale developed by (Allan & Meyer, 1990; Meyer, et. al., 1993), in measuring OC, which has been divided into three main components (affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment). There were six items measuring affective commitment, six items measuring continuance commitment, and six items measuring normative commitment. The survey form has been used as a key tool to collect data to measure organizational success at Sadat University in Egypt.

3.5.4. Organizational Success Scale

The researcher will depend on the scale developed by (Simon et al., 2011), in measuring organizational success, which has been divided into two main components (organizational survival and organizational growth). The 10-item scale organizational success section is based on Simon, et al., 2011. There were five items measuring organizational survival and five items measuring organizational growth. The survey form has been used as a key tool to collect data to measure organizational success at Sadat University in Egypt.

Responses to all items scales were anchored on a five (5) point Likert scale for each statement ranging from (5) “full agreement,” (4) for “agree,” (3) for “neutral,” (2) for “disagree,” and (1) for “full disagreement.”

3.6. Data Analysis and Testing Hypotheses

The researcher has employed the following methods: (1) Cronbach's alpha or ACC, (2) (MRA), and (3) F- test and T-test. All these tests are found in SPSS.

4. Hypotheses Testing

4.1. Evaluating Reliability

Before testing the hypotheses and research questions, the reliability of KM and OS were assessed to reduce errors of measuring and maximize constancy of these scales. To assess the reliability of the data, Cronbach’s alpha test was conducted.

Table (3) shows the reliability results for KM and OS. All items had alphas above 0.70 and were, therefore, excellent, according to Langdrige’s (2004) criteria.

Table (3) Reliability of LS, JS, OC and OS

Variables	The Dimension	Number of Statement	ACC
LS	Transactional Leadership Styles (TALS)	10	0.8925
	Transformational Leadership Styles (TFLS)	15	0.8845
	Total Measurement	25	0.9430
JS	Internal Satisfaction	5	0.8835
	External Satisfaction	5	0.9620
	Total Measurement	10	0.9591
OC	Affective Commitment	6	0.9716
	Continuance Commitment	6	0.8783
	Normative Commitment	6	0.9443
	Total Measurement	18	0.9753
OS	Organizational Survival	5	0.9192
	Organizational Growth	5	0.8856
	Total Measurement	10	0.9515

Regarding Table (3), the 25 items of LS are reliable because the ACC is 0.9430. Transactional Leadership Styles (TALS), which consists of 10 items, is reliable because the ACC is 0.8925.

Transformational Leadership Styles (TFLS), which consists of 15 items, is reliable because the ACC is 0.8845.

According to Table (3), the 10 items of JS are reliable because the ACC is 0.9591. The internal satisfaction, which consists of 5 items, is reliable because the ACC is 0.8835. The 5 items related to external satisfaction are reliable because ACC is 0.9620. Thus, the reliability of JS can be acceptable.

Regarding Table (3), the 18 items of OC are reliable because the ACC is 0.9753. Affective commitment, which consists of 6 items, is reliable because the ACC is 0.9716. Continuance commitment, which consists of 6 items, is reliable because the ACC is 0.8783. Furthermore, normative commitment, which consists of 6 items, is reliable because the ACC is 0.9443. Thus, the internal consistency of OC can be acceptable.

According to Table (3), the 10 items of OS are reliable because the ACC is 0.9515. The organizational survival, which consists of 5 items, is reliable because the ACC is 0.9192. The 5 items related to organizational growth are reliable because ACC is 0.8856. Thus, the reliability of OS can be acceptable.

Accordingly, four scales were defined, LS (25 variables), where ACC represented about 0.9430, JS (10) where ACC represented about 0.9591, OC (18) where ACC represented about 0.9753 and OS (10 variables), where ACC represented 0.9515.

4.2. Correlation Analysis

The researcher calculated means and standard deviations for each variable and created a correlation matrix of all variables used in hypothesis testing. Arithmetic mean and standard deviation values related to dependent and independent variables of this study and correlation coefficients between these variables are given in Table (4).

Table (4) Descriptive Statistics and Correlation Matrix of Constructs

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	1	2	3	4	5
1. Transactional Leadership Styles (TALS)	3.82	0.677	1				
2. Transformational Leadership Styles (TFLS)	3.84	0.594	0.963**	1			
3. Job Satisfaction	3.58	0.808	0.549**	0.562**	1		
4. Organizational Commitment	3.61	0.833	0.584**	0.591**	0.931**	1	
5. Organizational Success	3.57	0.886	0.388**	0.393**	0.644**	0.720**	1

Note: ** Correlation is significant at 0.01 level.

According to Table (4), the first issue examined was the different facets of LS. Among the various facets of LS, those who responded identified the presence of Transformational Leadership Styles (TFLS) (M=3.84, SD=0.594). This was followed by Transactional Leadership Styles (TALS) (M=3.82, SD=0.677).

The second issue examined was the different facets of JS (internal satisfaction and external satisfaction). Most of the respondents identified the overall JS (M=3.58, SD=0.808).

The third issue examined was the different facets of OC (affective commitment, continuance commitment and normative commitment). Most of the respondents identified the overall JS (M=3.61, SD=0.833).

The fourth issue examined was the different facets of OS (organizational survival, and organizational growth). Most of the respondents identified the overall OS (M=3.57, SD=0.886).

According to Table (4), LS dimensions have positive and significant relation with JS. The correlation between LS (TALS) and JS is 0.549. For LS (TFLS) and JS, the value is 0.562.

According to Table (4), LS dimensions have positive and significant relation with OC. The correlation between LS (TALS) and OC is 0.584. For LS (TFLS) and OC, the value is 0.591.

According to Table (4), JS dimensions have positive and significant relation with OS dimensions. The correlation between JS and OS is 0.644. For OC and OS show correlation value of 0.720.

Regarding Table (4), LS dimensions have positive and significant relation with OS dimensions. The correlation between LS (TALS) and OS is 0.388. For LS (TFLS) and OS, the value is 0.393.

Finally, Table (4) proves that there is a significant correlation between LS, JS, OC and OS. So our hypothesis is supported and it can be said that there is a significant correlation between LS, JS, OC and OS.

4.3. The Relationship between LS (TALS) and JS

The relationship between LS (TALS) and JS at Sadat University in Egypt is determined. The first hypothesis to be tested is:

There is no relationship between LS (TALS) and JS at Sadat University in Egypt.

Table (5) MRA Results for LS (TALS) and JS

The Variables of LS (TALS)	Beta	R	R ²
1. My supervisor tells me what needs to be done until I get a reward for the best.	0.694**	0.335	0.112
2. The effort I exert in my work is commensurate with the returns that I get.	0.343**	0.387	0.149
3. I negotiate with my supervisors on what I can get for my work.	0.603**	0.448	0.200
4. My direct supervisor has instructions to be flexible in granting rewards.	1.349**	0.533	0.284
5. The reward system is commensurate with the needs and wishes of the employees.	0.218	0.310	0.096
6. My supervisor requests only what is necessary to complete the work.	0.972*	0.524	0.274
7. I am encouraged by my supervisor to have initiative towards the development of the bank.	0.359**	0.405	0.164
8. My supervisor requests only what I should know to accomplish my work.	0.419	0.391	0.152
9. There is no need to inform my supervisor with all details of my work.	0.273*	0.269	0.072
10. My supervisor requests that I inform him about only things unplanned.	0.888**	0.365	0.133
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Multiple Correlation Coefficients ▪ Coefficient of Determination ▪ The Value of Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ The Value of Indexed F ▪ Level of Significant 		0.671	
		0.450	
		33.491	
		10.409	
		3.57	
		0.05	
** P < 0.01 * P < 0.05			

Table (5) proves that there is a relationship between LS (TALS) and JS at significance level of 0,000. As a result of the value of R², the 10 independent variables of LS (TALS) can explain 45% of the total differentiation in JS level.

For the results of a structural analysis of the MRA, the direct effect of LS (TALS) and JS is obtained. Because MCC is 0.671, it is concluded that there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

4.4. The Relationship between LS (TFLS) and JS

The relationship between LS (TFLS) and JS at Sadat University in Egypt is determined. The second hypothesis to be tested is:

There is no relationship between LS (TFLS) and JS at Sadat University in Egypt.

As Table (6) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.686. This means that JS has been significantly explained by the 15 independent variables of LS (TFLS).

Furthermore, the R² of 0.47 indicates that the percentage of the variable interprets the whole model, that is, 47%. It is evident that the 15 independent variables justified 47% of the total factors of JS. Hence, 53% are explained by the other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

Table (6) MRA Results for LS (TFLS) and JS

The Variables of LS (TFLS)	Beta	R	R ²
1. My supervisor is interested in employees believed to neglect their work.	0.015	0.130	0.016
2. My supervisor in the bank knows what I want and helps me to get it.	0.074	0.305	0.093
3. My supervisor is interested in assessment of employees when they do good work.	0.020	0.316	0.099
4. My supervisor is aware of the existence of differences in individual needs and wishes of the employees.	0.044	0.313	0.097
5. My supervisor works mainly on the development of employees by delegating powers.	0.124**	0.233	0.054
6. My supervisor encourages everyone around him to carry out the tasks entrusted to them.	0.685**	0.335	0.112
7. My supervisor is highly skillful in acquisition and loyalty of bank staff.	0.405	0.387	0.149
8. My supervisor has major potential to increase staff motivation and loyalty to the organization.	0.612**	0.448	0.200
9. My supervisor gives me a major opportunity to express my views for the development of the bank.	1.094*	0.533	0.284
10. My supervisor plays a role which is a model of respect for all employees.	0.198	0.310	0.096
11. My supervisor gives directives that force me to rethink some of my own work.	0.929*	0.524	0.274
12. My supervisor gives me a major opportunity to think about old problems in new ways.	0.345**	0.405	0.164
13. My supervisor provides me with new ways to develop my perspective on things.	0.476	0.391	0.152
14. My supervisor encourages employees to provide totally new ideas.	0.269*	0.269	0.072
15. My supervisor allows all employees to submit new ideas to solve business problems.	0.869**	0.365	0.133
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Multiple Correlation Coefficients ▪ Coefficient of Determination ▪ The Value of Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ The Value of Indexed F ▪ Level of Significant 		0.686 0.470 23.907 15, 404 3.57 0.05	
** P < 0.01 * P < 0.05			

4.5. The Relationship between LS (TALS) and OC

The relationship between LS (TALS) and OC at Sadat University in Egypt is determined. The first hypothesis to be tested is:

There is no relationship between LS (TALS) and OC at Sadat University in Egypt.

Table (7) proves that there is a relationship between LS (TALS) and OC at significance level of 0,000. As a result of the value of R², the 10 independent variables of LS (TALS) can explain 47.4% of the total differentiation in OC level.

For the results of a structural analysis of the MRA, the direct effect of LS (TALS) and OC is obtained. Because MCC is 0.688, it is concluded that there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

Table (7) MRA Results for LS (TALS) and OC

The Variables of LS (TALS)	Beta	R	R ²
1. My supervisor tells me what needs to be done until I get a reward for the best.	0.659**	0.344	0.118
2. The effort I exert in my work is commensurate with the returns that I get.	0.035	0.429	0.184
3. I negotiate with my supervisors on what I can get for my work.	0.501**	0.431	0.185
4. My direct supervisor has instructions to be flexible in granting rewards.	1.376**	0.588	0.345
5. The reward system is commensurate with the needs and wishes of the employees.	0.107	0.340	0.115
6. My supervisor requests only what is necessary to complete the work.	0.951*	0.580	0.336
7. I am encouraged by my supervisor to have initiative towards the development of the bank.	0.324*	0.405	0.164
8. My supervisor requests only what I should know to accomplish my work.	0.131	0.429	0.184
9. There is no need to inform my supervisor with all details of my work.	0.117	0.311	0.096
10. My supervisor requests that I inform him about only things unplanned.	0.852**	0.372	0.138
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Multiple Correlation Coefficients ▪ Coefficient of Determination ▪ The Value of Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ The Value of Indexed F ▪ Level of Significant 		0.688 0.474 36.849 10.409 3.57 0.05	
** P < 0.01 * P < 0.05			

4.6. The Relationship between LS (TFLS) and OC

The relationship between LS (TFLS) and OC at Sadat University in Egypt is determined. The second hypothesis to be tested is:

There is no relationship between LS (TFLS) and OC at Sadat University in Egypt.

As Table (8) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.699. This means that OC has been significantly explained by the 15 independent variables of LS (TFLS).

Furthermore, the R² of 0.488 indicates that the percentage of the variable interprets the whole model, that is, 48.8%.

It is evident that the 15 independent variables justified 48.8% of the total factors of OC.

Hence, 51.2% are explained by the other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

Table (8) MRA Results for LS (TFLS) and OC

The Variables of LS (TFLS)	Beta	R	R ²
1. My supervisor is interested in employees believed to neglect their work.	0.032	0.158	0.024
2. My supervisor in the bank knows what I want and helps me to get it.	0.059	0.322	0.103
3. My supervisor is interested in assessment of employees when they do good work.	0.029	0.331	0.109
4. My supervisor is aware of the existence of differences in individual needs and wishes of the employees.	0.015	0.298	0.088
5. My supervisor works mainly on the development of employees by delegating powers.	0.125**	0.277	0.051
6. My supervisor encourages everyone around him to carry out the tasks entrusted to them.	0.644**	0.344	0.118
7. My supervisor is highly skillful in acquisition and loyalty of bank staff.	0.087	0.429	0.184
8. My supervisor has major potential to increase staff motivation and loyalty to the organization.	0.515**	0.431	0.185
9. My supervisor gives me a major opportunity to express my views for the development of the bank.	1.209**	0.588	0.35
10. My supervisor plays a role which is a model of respect for all employees.	0.098	0.340	0.115
11. My supervisor gives directives that force me to rethink some of my own work.	0.792*	0.580	0.336
12. My supervisor gives me a major opportunity to think about old problems in new ways.	0.320*	0.405	0.164
13. My supervisor provides me with new ways to develop my perspective on things.	0.176	0.429	0.184
14. My supervisor encourages employees to provide totally new ideas.	0.100	0.311	0.096
15. My supervisor allows all employees to submit new ideas to solve business problems.	0.823	0.372	0.138
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Multiple Correlation Coefficients ▪ Coefficient of Determination ▪ The Value of Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ The Value of Indexed F ▪ Level of Significant 		0.699 0.488 25.711 15, 404 3.57 0.05	
** P < 0.01 * P < 0.05			

4.7. The Relationship between JS and OS

The relationship between JS and OS at Sadat University in Egypt is determined. The first hypothesis to be tested is:

There is no relationship between JS and OS at Sadat University in Egypt.

Table (9) MRA Results for JS and OS

The Variables of (JS)	Beta	R	R ²
1. Internal Satisfaction	0.369**	0.633	0.400
2. External Satisfaction	0.289**	0.626	0.391
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Multiple Correlation Coefficients ▪ Coefficient of Determination ▪ The Value of Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ The Value of Indexed F ▪ Level of Significant 		0.644 0.415 147.977 2, 417 3.57 0.05	
** P < 0.01			

Table (9) proves that there is a relationship between JS and OS at significance level of 0,000. As a result of the value of R^2 , the 5 independent variables of internal satisfaction can explain 41.5% of the total differentiation in OS level.

For the results of a structural analysis of the MRA, the direct effect of JS and OS is obtained. Because MCC is 0.644, it is concluded that there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

4.8. The Relationship between OC and OS

The relationship between OC and OS at Sadat University in Egypt is determined. The second hypothesis to be tested is:

There is no relationship between OC and OS at Sadat University in Egypt.

Table (10) The Relationship between OC and OS

The Variables of OC	Beta	R	R^2
1. Affective Commitment	0.203*	0.698	0.487
2. Continuance Commitment	0.030	0.650	0.422
3. Normative Commitment	0.508**	0.722	0.521
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Multiple Correlation Coefficients ▪ Coefficient of Determination ▪ The Value of Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ The Value of Indexed F ▪ Level of Significant 		0.727	
		0.528	
		155.120	
		3, 416	
		3.57	
		0.05	
** P < 0.01 * P < 0.05			

As Table (10) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.727. This means that OS has been significantly explained by the 18 independent variables of JA (OC).

Furthermore, the R^2 of 0.528 indicates that the percentage of the variable interprets the whole model, that is, 52.8%. It is evident that the 18 independent variables justified 52.8% of the total factors of OS. Hence, 47.2% are explained by the other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

4.9. The Relationship between LS (TALS) and OS

The relationship between LS (TALS) and OS at Sadat University in Egypt is determined. The first hypothesis to be tested is:

There is no relationship between LS (TALS) and OS at Sadat University in Egypt.

Table (11) proves that there is a relationship between LS (TALS) and OS at significance level of 0,000. As a result of the value of R^2 , the 10 independent variables of LS (TALS) can explain 24.1% of the total differentiation in OS level.

For the results of a structural analysis of the MRA, the direct effect of LS (TALS) and OS is obtained. Because MCC is 0.491, it is concluded that there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

Table (11) MRA Results for LS (TALS) and OS

The Variables of LS (TALS)	Beta	R	R ²
1. My supervisor tells me what needs to be done until I get a reward for the best.	0.473*	0.244	0.059
2. The effort I exert in my work is commensurate with the returns that I get.	0.060	0.266	0.070
3. I negotiate with my supervisors on what I can get for my work.	0.377**	0.251	0.063
4. My direct supervisor has instructions to be flexible in granting rewards.	0.850*	0.439	0.192
5. The reward system is commensurate with the needs and wishes of the employees.	0.117	0.213	0.045
6. My supervisor requests only what is necessary to complete the work.	0.479	0.433	0.187
7. I am encouraged by my supervisor to have initiative towards the development of the bank.	0.317*	0.232	0.055
8. My supervisor requests only what I should know to accomplish my work.	0.077	0.265	0.070
9. There is no need to inform my supervisor with all details of my work.	0.134	0.205	0.042
10. My supervisor requests that I inform him about only things unplanned.	0.617*	0.265	0.070
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Multiple Correlation Coefficients ▪ Coefficient of Determination ▪ The Value of Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ The Value of Indexed F ▪ Level of Significant 		0.491 0.241 13.012 10.409 3.57 0.05	
** P < 0.01 * P < 0.05			

4.10. The Relationship between LS (TFLS) and OS

The relationship between LS (TFLS) and OS at Sadat University in Egypt is determined. The second hypothesis to be tested is:

There is no relationship between LS (TFLS) and OS at Sadat University in Egypt.

As Table (12) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.505. This means that OS has been significantly explained by the 15 independent variables of LS (TFLS).

Furthermore, the R² of 0.256 indicates that the percentage of the variable interprets the whole model, that is, 25.6%. It is evident that the 15 independent variables justified 25.6% of the total factors of OS. Hence, 47.4% are explained by the other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

Table (12) The Relationship between LS (TFLS) and OS

The Variables of LS (TFLS)	Beta	R	R ²
1. My supervisor is interested in employees believed to neglect their work.	0.064	0.161	0.025
2. My supervisor in the bank knows what I want and helps me to get it.	0.093	0.173	0.029
3. My supervisor is interested in assessment of employees when they do good work.	0.001	0.207	0.042
4. My supervisor is aware of the existence of differences in individual needs and wishes of the employees.	0.007	0.225	0.050
5. My supervisor works mainly on the development of employees by delegating powers.	0.099*	0.156	0.024
6. My supervisor encourages everyone around him to carry out the tasks entrusted to them.	0.360	0.244	0.059
7. My supervisor is highly skillful in acquisition and loyalty of bank staff.	0.11**4	0.266	0.070
8. My supervisor has major potential to increase staff motivation and loyalty to the organization.	0.407**	0.251	0.063
9. My supervisor gives me a major opportunity to express my views for the development of the bank.	0.674	0.439	0.192
10. My supervisor plays a role which is a model of respect for all employees.	0.116	0.213	0.045
11. My supervisor gives directives that force me to rethink some of my own work.	0.313	0.433	0.187
12. My supervisor gives me a major opportunity to think about old problems in new ways.	0.322*	0.232	0.053
13. My supervisor provides me with new ways to develop my perspective on things.	0.145	0.265	0.070
14. My supervisor encourages employees to provide totally new ideas.	0.154	0.205	0.042
15. My supervisor allows all employees to submit new ideas to solve business problems.	0.486*	0.265	0.070
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Multiple Correlation Coefficients ▪ Coefficient of Determination ▪ The Value of Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ The Value of Indexed F ▪ Level of Significant 		0.505	
		0.256	
		9.233	
		15,404	
		3.57	
		0.05	
** P < 0.01 * P < 0.05			

5. Research Findings

This study on the mediating significant role of JA (JS and OC) in the relationship between LS and OS at Sadat University in Egypt has revealed a host of results. The most important findings are summed up as follows:

1. There is a statistically significant relationship between the dimensions of LS (TALS and TFLS) and JS at Sadat University in Egypt.
2. There is a positive relationship between the dimensions of LS (TALS and TFLS) and OC at Sadat University in Egypt.
3. There is a statistically significant relationship between the dimensions of JS (internal satisfaction and eternal satisfaction) and OS at Sadat University in Egypt.
4. There is a positive relationship between the dimensions of OC (affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment) and OS at Sadat City University in Egypt.
5. There is a significant relationship between the dimensions of LS (TALS and TFLS) and OS at Sadat University in Egypt.
6. There is a significant role of JA (JS and OC) in the relationship between LS and OS at Sadat University in Egypt.

6. Recommendations

Empirical results validate the notion that effective TALS and TFLS may lead towards OS. Therefore, the manager needs to take the following factors into account:

1. Organizations should place an emphasis on creating meaningful mission and vision statements that are specific, measurable, attainable, results-driven, and time sensitive. Based upon the mission and vision statements, organizational leaders can create team objectives for each functional area within an organization.
2. TFLS should be facilitated with TALS where applicable. Rewards such as praise and recognition need to be provided in a personalized way for OS.
3. Supervisors need to apply the best LS with the environment employees are working in.
4. It is necessary to pay more attention to OS at Sadat University in Egypt. Its officials should realize and spend lavishly on the important OS. This will achieve success currently and in the future, besides attaining the competitive advantage.
5. Reviewing the methods for selecting administrative leaders of Sadat University, and the need for attention by choosing individuals with excellent interpersonal skills, out of the importance of leadership in achieving the OS.
6. Taking care of management of Sadat University, the importance of a TALS in general, and contingent reward, in particular, as it is one of the important elements that can be used to increase OS.
7. The concerned department of Sadat University should heed the importance of management by exception as one of the elements leading to the achievement of OS. This can be achieved through expansion in the granting of authority to employees and encouragement of initiative and innovation in the ways and methods of work, including raising the quality and efficiency of performance.
8. Paying attention to Sadat University and TFLS in order to achieve the best response to the needs and wishes of employees to increase their contribution to the achievement of OS, on the one hand, and raise the performance level of Sadat University and strengthen their competitiveness, on the other hand.
9. Sadat University should pay more attention to OS. This may be accomplished through various means, which include (1) searching for experienced persons in modern management, (2) recognizing the desires and needs of employees, and (3) granting employees more authority for urging them to provide new development in their specialization.

7. Recommendation for Future Research

The present study has attempted to disclose the leadership styles and organizational learning at Sadat University in Egypt, but the scope of the study indicates the existence of other fields for prospective studies of no less importance in this field, including: (1) the impact of LS on quality work life, (2) the role played by TALS and TFLS in the relationship between OL, job performance and job satisfaction, (3) OL and its impact on some variables like job empowerment, organizational culture, and (4) Such studies may be adopted on various communities like universities, directorates of education and public and private hospitals.

References

- Al-Ajmi, R. (2006). The effect of gender on job satisfaction and organizational commitment in Kuwait. *International Journal of Management*, 23(4), 838-844.
- Allen, N., and Meyer, J., (1990). The measurement and antecedents of affective, continuance and normative commitment to the organization. *Journal of Occupational Psychology*, 63, 1-18.
- Ambrosini V., (2003). *Tacit and Ambiguous Resource as Source of Competitive Advantage*, Palgrave Macmillan, UK.
- Avolio B., and Bass B. (2002). *Developing Potential Across a Full Range of Leadership*. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, 179 pages.
- Awad, T., and Alhashemi, S. (2012). Assessing the Effect of Interpersonal Communications on Employees' Commitment and Satisfaction. *International Journal of Islamic and Middle Eastern Finance and Management*, 58(2), 134-156.
- Ayeni, C., and Phopoola, S., (2007). 'Work Motivation, Job Satisfaction, and Organizational Commitment of Library Personnel in Academic and Research Libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria', *Library Philosophy and Practice*.

- Bartlett, K. R. (2001). The relationship between training and organizational commitment: A study in the health care field. *Human Resource Development Quarterly*, 12(4), 335-361.
- Bass, B. and Avolio, B. (1990). The implications of transactional and transformational leadership for individual, team, and organizational development. In R. W. Woodman and W. A. Pasmore (Eds.), *Research in organizational change and development*, (4), 231-272. Greenwich, CT: JAI Press.
- Bateman, T. and Strasser S. (1984). A longitudinal analysis of the antecedents of organizational commitment. *Academy of Management Journal*, 27 (1), PP. 95-112.
- Best M, and Thurston N., (2004). Measuring Nurse Job Satisfaction, *Journal of Nursing Administration*, 34:283-290.
- Bhuiyan S., and Menguc B. (2002). An Extension and Evaluation of Job Characteristics, Organizational Commitment and Job Satisfaction in an Expatriate, Guest Worker, Sales Setting. *Journal of Personal Selling and Sales Management*, 22(1), 1-11.
- Boseman, G. (2008). Effective leadership in a changing world. *Journal of Financial Service Professionals*, 62(3), 36-38.
- Brewer, A. (1996). Developing Commitment Between Managers and Employees. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 11(4), 24-34. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/02683949610117599>
- Churchill G., Ford N., and Walker O., (1974), "Measuring the Job Satisfaction of Industrial Salesmen," *Journal of Marketing Research*, 11, 254-60.
- Crossman, A., and Abou -Zaki, B. (2003). Job satisfaction and employee performance of Lebanese banking staff. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 18 (4), 368-376. doi: 0.1108/026839403104731
- Dell, D., and Kramer, R., (2003). Forging Strategic Business Alignment", The conference board, www.conferenceboard.org.
- Dendaas, N. (2004). The scholarship related to nursing work environments: Where do we go from here? *Advances in Nursing Science*, 27, 12–20.
- Desselle, S. (1998). New York State Pharmacists: Relationship Between Job Satisfaction. *Workplace Climate, Commitment, and Providing Pharmaceutical Care*, *New York State Pharmacist Century II*, 72, PP. 27-29.
- Dubin, R., Champoux, J. E. and Porter, L. W. (1975) "Central Life Interests and Organizational Commitment of Blue-Collar and Clerical Workers" *Administrative Science Quarterly*, September (20): 411-421
- Elbert, R., and Griffin, R. (2005). *Business Essentials* (5th ed.). New Jersey, Pearson Education.
- Farsi Z, Dehghan-Nayeri N, Negarandeh R, Broomand S. (2010). Nursing profession in Iran: an overview of opportunities and challenges. *Jon J NURS Sci* 2010; 7(1): 9-18.
- Finn C. (2001). Autonomy: An Important Component for Nurses' Job Satisfaction. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, 38(3), 349-57.
- Franken, A., Edwards, C., and Lambert, R. (2009). Executing strategic change: Understanding the critical management Elements that lead to success. *California Management Review*, 51 (3), pp. 49-73.
- George, J. and Jones , G. (1997). Experiencing work: Values, attitudes, and moods. *Human Relations*, 50 , 393-416.
- Grant, R., (2000). *Contemporary Strategy Analysis*, Oxford, UK.
- Greenberg, J., and Baron, R. (2003). *Behaviour in Organizations: Understanding and Managing the Human Side of Work* (8th ed.). Upper Saddle River, Pearson Education, Inc.
- Hallowell, E. (2011). *Shine: Using brain science to get the best from your people*. Harvard, MA: Harvard Business Review.
- Hechanova, M., Alampay, R., and Franco, E., (2006). Psychological empowerment, job satisfaction, and performance among Filipino service workers. *Asian Journal of Social Psychology*, 9, 72-78.
- Hill, C., and Jones, G., (2001). *Strategic management Theory* , Houghton Mifflin co. New York, USA .
- Homburg, C., and Stock, R. (2004). The Link Between Salespeoples Job Satisfaction and Customer Satisfaction in a Business-to-Business Context: a Dyadic Analysis. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science* , 32(2), 144-158.
- Hong, L, While, A., and Barriball, K. (2005). Job Satisfaction among Nurses: A Literature Review. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, 42(2), 211-227. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2004.09.003>

- Hunt, S. Vood, V. and Chonko, L. (1989), “Corporate Ethical Values and Organizational Commitment in Marketing”, *The Journal of Marketing*, 53(3): 79-90
- Hussami, M. (2008). A Study of Nurses' Job Satisfaction: The Relationship to Organizational Commitment, Perceived Organizational Support, Transactional Leadership, Transformational Leadership and Level of Education. *European Journal of Scientific Research*, 22(2), 286-295.
- Ivancevich, J., and Matteson, M. (2002). *Organizational Behaviour and Management* (6th ed.). New York, McGraw-Hill.
- Ivey, G. and Kline, T. (2010). Transformational and active transactional leadership in the Canadian military. *Leadership and Organizational Development Journal*, 31(3), 246-262. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/01437731011039352>
- Jago, A. (1982). Leadership: Perspectives in theory and research. *Management Science*, 28 (3), pp. 315–336. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.28.3.315>
- Jalonen, P., Virtanen, M., and Vantera, J. (2006). Predictor of sustained organizational commitment among nurses with temporary job contacts. *Journal of Nursing Administration* 36(5), 268-276.
- Jehn, K., Northcraft, G. and Neale, M. (1999). Why differences make a difference: A field study of diversity, conflict, and performance in workgroups. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 44, 741-763.
- Jernigan, I., Beggs, J., and Kohut, G. (2002). Dimensions of Work Satisfaction as Predictor of Commitment Type. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 17(7), 546-579. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/02683940210444030>
- Joiner, T., Bakalis, S., (2006) "The antecedents of organizational commitment: the case of Australian casual academics", *International Journal of Educational Management*, Vol. 20 Iss: 6, pp.439 – 452.
- Judge, T., Thoresen, J., Bono, E., and Patton, G., (2001). The Job Satisfaction-Job Performance Relationship: A Qualitative and Quantitative Review, *Psychological Bulletin*, 127 (3), PP. 376-407.
- Jung, D., and Avolio, B. (2000). Opening the black box: An experimental investigation of the mediating effects of trust and value congruence on transformational and transactional leadership. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 21(8). PP. 949-964.
- Kenny, G. (2001). *Strategic Factor: Developing and Measure Winning Strategy*, 1st Ed., President Press, National Library of Australia.
- Kirkman, B., Chen, G., Farh, J., Chen, Z., and Lowe, K. (2009). Individual power distance orientation and follower reactions to transformational leaders: A cross level, cross-cultural examination. *Academy of Management Journal*, 52(4), pp. 744–764. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5465/AMJ.2009.43669971>
- Kouzes, J., and Posner, B. (2003). *Encouraging the heart*. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- Kreitner, R., and Kinicki, A. (2004). *Organizational behavior* (5th ed.). New York:Mc Graw-Hill Inc
- Lado, A., Boyd, N., and Wright, P. (1992). A competency-based model of sustainable competitive advantage: Towards a conceptual integration. *Journal of Management*, 18, 77-91. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/014920639201800106>
- Lambert, G., Hogan, L., and Griffin, L. (2007). The impact of distributive and procedural justice on correctional staff job stress, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment. *Journal of Criminal Justice*, 35, 644-656.
- Lane K, Esser J, Holte B, McCusker M., (2010). A study of nurse faculty job satisfaction in community colleges in Florida. *Teach. Learn. Nurs.*, 5: 16-26.
- Lee, K., Allen, N., Meyer, J., and Rhee, K., (2001) ‘The three-component model of organizational commitment: An application to South Korea’, *Applied Psychology: An International Review*, 50: 596–614.
- Locke, E. (1976). The Nature and Causes of Job Satisfaction, In M.D. Dunnette (Ed.), *Handbook of Industrial and Organizational Psychology*. Chicago: Rand-McNally.
- MacKensie, S., Podsakoff, P., and Ahearne, M. (1998). Some Possible Antecedents and Consequences of In-Role and Extra-Role Salesperson Performance. *Journal of Marketing*, 62, 87-98.
- Meyer, J. and Allen, N. (1991). A three component conceptualization of organizational commitment. *Human Resource Management Review*, 1: 61- 89.

- Meyer, J., and Allen, N. (1988). Links between Work Experience and Organizational Commitment During the First Year of Employment: A Longitudinal Analysis. *Journal of Occupational Psychology*, 61, 195-209. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.2044-8325.1988.tb00284.x>
- Meyer, J., Stanley, D., Herscovitch, L., and Topolnytsky, L. (2002). Affective, Continuance, and Normative Commitment to the Organization: A Meta-Analysis of Antecedents, Correlates, and Consequences. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 61, 20-52. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1006/jvbe.2001.1842>
- Meyer, J. Allen, N. and Smith, C. (1993). Commitment To Organizations And Occupations: Extension And Test Of A Three-Component Conceptualization”, *Journal Of Applied Psychology*, Vol. 78, Pp. 538-51.
- Meyer, J. Stanley, D. Herscovitch, L. and Topolnytsky L., (2002). Affective, Continuance, and Normative Commitment to the Organization: A Meta-analysis of Antecedents, Correlates, and Consequences”, *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 61,20-52.
- Mowday, R. (1998). Reflection on the Study and Relevance of Organizational Commitment”, *Human Resource Management*, 8(4): 387.401.
- Mowday, R., Porter, L. and Steers, R. (1982), *Employee-Organization Linkages: The Psychology of Commitment, Absenteeism and Turnover*, Academic Press, New York, NY.
- Mowday, R., Steers, R., and Porter, L. (1979). The Measurement of Organizational Commitment. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 14(3), 224-247. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0001-8791\(79\)90072-1](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0001-8791(79)90072-1)
- Netemeyer, R. G., Boles, J. S., McKee, D. O., and McMurrian, R. (1997). An investigation into the antecedents of organizational citizenship behaviors in a personal selling context. *Journal of Marketing*, 61 , 85-98.
- Noel, M., Hammel R., and Bootman J. (1982). Job Satisfaction among Hospital Pharmacy Personnel. *American Journal of Health-System Pharmacy*, 39(4), 600- 606.
- Omar N. Woody O. and Robert A. (2008). Beyond the Three-Component Model of Organizational Commitment, *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 9 (1), PP. 70-83.
- Oncel, S., Ozer, Z. C., and Efe, E. (2007). Work-related Stress, Burnout and Job Satisfaction in Turkish Midwives. *Social Behavior and Personality*, 35(3), 317-328.
- Oshagbemi, T. (2003). Personal Correlates of Job Satisfaction: Empirical Evidence from UK Universities, *International Journal of Social Economics*, 30(12): 1210-1232.
- Park, E., and Deitz, D. (2006). The effect of working relationship quality on salesperson performance and job satisfaction: Adaptive selling behavior in Korean automobile sales representatives. *Journal of Business Research*, 59, 204-213.
- Popper, M., andLipshitz, R. (2000). Installing mechanisms and instilling values: The role of leaders in organizational learning. *The Learning Organization*, 7(3), 135-144. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/09696470010335854>
- Porter, W., Steers, M., Mowday, R. and Boulian, V. (1974). Organizational commitment, job satisfaction, and turnover among psychiatric technicians. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 59(5), 603–609.
- Pounder, J. (2008). Transformational leadership: Practicing what we teach in the Management classroom. *Journal of Education for Business*, 84 (1), pp. 2-6. Rhodes, J.,<http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/09585190802051477>
- Rahim A. (1982). Demographic Variables in General Job Satisfaction in a Hospital: A Multivariate Study. *Percept and Motor Skills*, 55(3), 711–719.
- Raju, P., and Srivastava, R. (1994). Factors Contributing to Commitment to the Teaching Profession. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 8(5), 7-13. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/09513549410065684>
- Randall, D. M. (1987), “Commitment and the Organization: the Organization Man Revisited”, *The Academy of Management Review*, 12(3): 460–471
- Rashid, M., Zabid, Sambasivan, M., Johari J. (2003). The Influence of Corporate Culture and Organizational Commitment on Performance. *Journal of Management Development* 22 (8): 708-728.
- Rhodes, C., Brundrett, M., Nevill, A., (2008). Leadership Talent Identification and Development, *Educational Management Administration Leadership* July, Vol. 36, (3), PP. 311-335.

- Riaz, A., and Haider, M. (2010). Role of transformational and transactional leadership on job satisfaction and career satisfaction. *Business and Economic Horizons*, 1(1), 29-38.
- Robbins, P. (2000), *Essentials of Organizational Behavior*, 6th Ed., Prentice Hall, New Jersey.
- Robert P., (1983). Brodard et Taupin, Paris. France.
- Rosser, V. (2004). Faculty members' intentions to leave: a national study on their work life and satisfaction', *Research in Higher Education*, 45 (3), 285–309.
- Rothmann, S., and Coetzer, E. (2002). The Relationship between Personality Dimensions and Job Satisfaction. *Business Dynamics*, 11(1), 29-42.
- Rowe, W. (2001). Creating wealth in organizations: The role of strategic leadership. *Academy of Management Executive*, 15, 81-94. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5465/AME.2001.4251395>
- Saari, L., and Judge, T. (2004). Employee Attitudes and Job Satisfaction. *Human Resource Management*, 43(4), 395-407.
- Sarros, J., and Santora, J. (2001). The transformational-transactional leadership model in practice. *Leadership and Organization Development Journal*, 22 (8), 383-393. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/01437730110410107>
- Schermerhorn, J., Hunt, J., and R. Osborn. (1997). *Organizational Behavior*. J.W. and Sons, Inc., New York.
- Schwartz, T., Jones, J., and McCarthy, C. (2010). *The way we're working isn't working*. New York, NY: Free Press.
- Schwepker, C. (2001). Ethical Climate's Relationship to Job Satisfaction, Organizational Commitment, and Turnover Intention in Salesforce. *Journal of Business Research*, 54, 39-72.
- Sempene, M., Rieger, H., and Roodt, G. (2002). Job Satisfaction in Relation to Organizational Culture. *South African Journal of Industrial Psychology*, 28(2), 23-30.
- Sharma, J., and Bajpai, N. (2010). Organizational Commitment and its Impact on Job Satisfaction of Employees: A Comparative Study in India. *International Bulletin of Business Administration*, 9, 7-19.
- Silverthorne, C. (2004). The Impact of Organizational Culture and Person Organization Fit on Organizational Commitment and Job Satisfaction in Taiwan. *The Leadership and Organization Development Journal*, 25(7), 522-599. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/01437730410561477>
- Simon, A., Kumar, V., Schoeman, P., Moffat, P., Power, D., (2011). Strategic capabilities and their relationship to organizational success and its measures: Some pointers from five Australian studies", *Management Decision*, Vol. 49 No. 8, PP. 305 - 1326
- Smith, P.C., L.M. Kendall, and C.L. Hulin (1969). *The Measurement of Satisfaction in Work and Retirement*. Chicago: Rand McNally.
- Spagnoli, Paola, Caetano, Antonio and Santos, Susana Correia (2012), "Satisfaction with Job Aspects: Do Patterns Change over Time?", *Journal of Business Research*, 65(5): 609-16.
- Spector, P. (1997). *Job Satisfaction: Application, Assessment, Causes and Consequences*. California, Sage.
- Steer, M. R. (1977), "Antecedents and Outcomes of Organizational Commitment", *Administrative Sciences Quarterly*, 22(1): 46.56.
- Stewart J. (1983). Hospital Pharmacists' Job Satisfaction: A Review of the Data. *Topics in Hospital Pharmacy Management*, 3(1), 1-9.
- Stone, A., Russell, R., and Patterson, K. (2004). Transformational versus servant leadership: A difference in leader focus. *Leadership and Organization Development Journal*, 25(4), 349-361. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/01437730410538671>
- Vecchio, R., Justin, J., and Pearce, C. (2008). The utility of transactional and transformational leadership for predicting performance and satisfaction within a path-goal theory framework. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 81 (1), pp. 71–82. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1348/096317907X202482>
- Vera, D., and Crossan, M. (2004). Strategic leadership and organizational learning. *Academy of Management Review*, 29 (2), PP. 222-240
- Vitell, S.J. and A. Singhapakdi (2007), 'The Role of Ethics Institutionalization in Influencing Organizational Commitment, Job Satisfaction, and Esprit de Corps', *Journal of Business Ethics* 81, 343-353.
- Wagner C. (2007). Organizational Commitment as Aa Predictor Variable in Nursing Turnover Research: Literature Review. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 60, 235-247.

- Walumbwa, F., Avolio, B., and Zhu, W. (2008). How transformational leadership weaves its influence on individual job performance: the role of identification and efficacy beliefs. *Personnel Psychology*, 61(4), pp. 793–825. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1744-6570.2008.00131.x>
- Webster's Merriam Co. (1974), USA.
- Weis, H. (2002) 'Deconstructing job satisfaction: separating, evaluation, beliefs, and affective experiences', *Human Resource Management Review*, 3, 12–22.
- Whetten, D., (1987). Organizational Growth and Decline Processes, *Annual Review of Sociology*, Vol.13, PP. 335-358.
- Wilson, P. (1996). Job Satisfaction: A review of the Literature: December 14 2001. (Online). Available: <http://www.geocities.com/paris/cafe/5839/writings/satisfactio/html>.
- Wood, Van R. (1986). Job Satisfaction Survey. ETS Tracking Number: TC017396.
- Xirasagar, S. (2008). Transformational, transactional and laissez-faire leadership among physician executives. *Journal of Health Organization and Management*, 22(6), 599-613. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/14777260810916579>
- Zarea K, Negarandeh R, Dehghan-Nayeri N, Rezaei-Adaryani M. (2009). Nursing staff shortages and job satisfaction in Iran: Issues and challenges. *Nurs health sci*; 11(3): 326–31.
- Zeytinoglu, I. U., Denton , M., Davies, S., Baumann, A., Blythe, J., and Boos, L. (2007). Associations between work intensification, stress, and job satisfaction, the case of nurses in Ontario. *Relations Industrielles*, 62(2), 201.
- Zhu, W., Chew, I., and Spangler, W. (2005). CEO transformational leadership and organizational outcomes: The mediating role of human-capital-enhancing human resource management. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 16, 39-52. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.leaqua.2004.06.001>